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Field Monitoring on Some Major Insect Pests of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) in Jega, Kebbi, Nigeria

¹*Kwaifa, N. M., S. Umar² & I. J. Yusuf²

¹Crop Science Department,
Faculty of Agriculture,
Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension,
Faculty of Agriculture,
Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: nasirkwafa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pests are among the major constraints to agriculture that continuously caused detrimental losses and economic damages to Agricultural products thereby, decreasing the economic and financial gains throughout the world. Protection against pests such as insects of the cultivated crops is therefore of paramount importance to ensure adequate food supply, food security, industrial raw materials and their continuous availability for a sustainable economic growth and development. Timely monitoring of insect pests became very necessary to effectively plan efficient insect pests control strategies. Despite the serious damages and losses caused by these insect pests on important crops such as Tomato, there is no adequate information and data on the exact types of insect pest that attack the crop in Jega, Kebbi, Nigeria. The study is aimed at finding the exact insect pests of tomato and the actual time of abundance of the major insects affecting tomato plant in the study location so as to allow for efficient control of these insect pests at the right time which will greatly assist in reducing the effect of their infestation on tomato plants in the study location. This will greatly lead to increase in tomato yield for higher production and profitability. A study was conducted in the dry and rainy seasons of 2024, at the University Teaching and Research Farm, Jega Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Jega (Latitude 12° 11' N; Longitude 4° 16' E) to identify and monitor the abundance of the major insect pests of tomato in the study location. Sampling of insects were conducted through visual count method. Experiments was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Results revealed three major insect pests identified and monitored on tomato namely; Leafhopper (*Empoasca fabae*), Aphid (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*) and Whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*). The abundance of *E. fabae* was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher on tomato plants than all the other insect monitored in both seasons, with *M. euphorbiae* being the second in abundance and the third in abundance was *B. tabaci* that was significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower than *E. fabae* and *M. euphorbiae* in abundance on tomato. Environmental temperature and the relative humidity significantly correlated positively ($P < 0.05$) with tomato insect pest abundance in the study field with the exception of rainfall that correlated significantly ($P < 0.05$) negative with the abundance all the insects monitored. *Bemisia tabaci* abundance was found to be positively correlated with both temperature and relative humidity but negatively correlated with rainfall. The result of this study provides the first documented

information obtained from research results that will assist in formulating an effective tomato insect pest management and control strategy in the studied area.

Keywords: Tomato; Insects; Monitoring; Seasons; Abundance; Field.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is among the most important vegetable crops valued and produced all over the world today, with an average yield of about 100 million tons from 3.7 million hectares of cultivated land, tomato ranks second after potato according to the area cultivated (FAOSTAT, 2023). In Africa the crop is commonly cultivated around Guinea Savannah mostly in the wet season and Sudan Savannah in the dry season through irrigation scheme (Enujeke and Emuh, 2015) and Willa Dunn *et al.* (2020). In Africa the average yield of 8-25 t ha⁻¹ was recorded, with the highest yield from South Africa and the least from Benin and Nigeria (Umeh *et al.*, 2002; Maina and Maina, 2012). Tomato is produced for several years by farmers in Nigeria but with yields usually that are lower between 5-20 tones/ha, because of using lower yielding crop varieties, low soil fertility, weed, diseases and insect infestation (Akintoye, 2003 and Olaniyi *et al.*, 2010). Nigeria is the highest country in terms of population in Africa also the 7th most populous the world over and is expected to reach over 400 million by the year 2050, meeting the domestic demand for foods therefore is the most challenging. Tomato which is a basic part a staple foods of the majority of the population in Nigeria, thus making it availability very crucial (Edon, 2016). Among the highly damaging and most notorious problems affecting tomato in Nigeria are the different insect pests that annually destroyed the crop on the farms. Notably, whitefly is *B. tabaci*, was found to be a major insect pest o tomato the world over and Nigeria may not be an exception, which can feed from over 500 different host plants such as Tomato; *Solanum lycopersicum*, Peppers; *Capsicum spp.*, Cassava; *Manihot esculenta*, Cotton; *Gossypium spp.*, Sweet potato; *Ipomoea batatas*, Tobacco; *Nicotiana tabacum*, Okra; *Abelmoschus esculentus* and Eggplant; *Solanum melongena* among others, causing serious damages of up to 100% in some of these crops all over the world, with this insect having approximately 41 morphologically indistinguishable biotypes (De Barro *et al.*, 2011). During feeding the pest transmits viral disease such as Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Disease (TYLCD) and Tomato Mottle Disease Virus (ToMoD) on major crop plants; including tomato, cassava, cotton, okra, tobacco and sweet potato in Nigeria leading to serious damages on the crop and subsequently, killing the plants. Direct feeding damage is not usually of importance, but viruses transmitted during feeding can cause serious yield losses (Moshe *et al.*, 2014).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

These studies were conducted at the Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Teaching and Research Farm, Jega (Latitude 12° 11' N; Longitude 4° 16' E) in 2024, within the dry and rainy seasons of 2024 in the field. The area lies within the Sudan Savannah Agro-ecological zone of Nigeria, characterized by erratic and scanty rainfall that lasts for about 6 months. With a semi-arid climatic condition and average annual rainfall between 787.53-112.21mm. Having a relative humidity that ranges from 21-47% and 51-79% in the wet and dry spells, in that order. Temperature averages between 14-43°C during the dry season and 27-41°C during the rainy season (Eberibe *et al.*, 2017).

Coordinates: (Latitude 12° 11' N; Longitude 4° 16' E)

Map of Jega Town in Kebbi State Nigeria.

Land clearing was performed by cutting and clearing of weeds from the experimental site, a tractor was used to plough the larger soil clods raised during harrowing to enhance moisture for plant growth. The land was then levelled by moving soil producing a gentle land slope for gravity flow to facilitate water flow. Tomato variety (Roma VFN) was obtained from the Kebbi Agricultural Supply Company (KASCOM). Seedlings were nursed in a nursery bed employing the nursery practices and techniques, transplanted at about 21 days after sowing. Sunken beds of 2 x 1 m were constructed, with the soil made into fine tilt after removing large stone stumps, irrigated using a watering can. Seeds were broadcasted in beds and mulched with millet stalk and watered. The soil was thoroughly mixed with farmyard manure at the rate of 4 tons per hectare. One week after germination the mulched material was gradually removed. Transplanted at 30-35 days post planting and transplanted in a row at a spacing of 40 cm intra and 60 cm inter row at 2 weeks after sowing and weeding was done when necessary (Muhammad and Singh, 2007).

Experimental design and Data collections

The farm consisted of four main plots represented as replications, with four sub-plot sizes of 3m x 3m (Area =9m²) each, consisting of 5 rows per plot containing 5 plants per each row giving plants population per plot spaced at 60x30 cm. Each Block is divided into three sub-plots replicated four times giving a total of 12 smaller plots containing 25 tomato plants each in an open field, laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Data was obtained from each main plot from the 3 randomly selected plants per the 3 main plots. Data obtained was subjected to the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and means found to be significant were subjected to the Least Significant Difference (LSD at 0.05%) level of significance.

Identification of insect pests

The different types of insect pests seen on tomato plant (Roma variety) were picked in the experimental field on tomato plants at two weeks after transplanting up to 12 weeks for two planting cycles (dry and

rainy seasons) per each year. For identification the insect pests seen on tomato plants were visually sampled using the Sweep-net (less than 6.0 mm) and seen with the aid of a Hand lenses. Sampled insects were transferred into separate plastic containers and stored in 70% ethanol and taken to the National Insect Museum of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria, where the sampled insects were identified using the Dichotomous Insect Taxonomic Keys (Zim and Cottam, 2000), which formed the basis for identification the insects obtained in the study location.

Visual insect count

Sampling of the insect pests on tomato was performed by visual counting method adopted from Naranjo and Flint (1995). The exercise was performed in the early morning hours between 6:00–8:00 am when the insects were less mobile (Oparaeke et al., 2005). Sampling was performed weekly on Saturdays on 5 randomly selected and tagged tomato plants for taking insect counts using the leaf turn method.

RESULTS

Overall insect pests identified and their mean abundance on tomato plants during the study period in the study location

As presented in Table 3.1, the species *E. fabae* (Leafhopper) had the highest number in abundance in the dry season (35.8%) and rainy (33.6%) seasons. Indicating that *E. fabae* was the most prevalent insect pest species, than all others recorded on the tomato crop during the study period at the study location. Next to this in decreasing succession, were *M. euphorbiae* in the dry season (31.4%) and rainy season (17.2%), the third most abundant insect was *B. tabaci* with a dry season abundance of 31.4% and rainy season recorded 17.2% of the total abundance found on tomato plants in both seasons. However, *E. fabae* and *B. tabaci* were observed to have a numerically higher population in the dry season than that of the rainy season in both years. However, a contrasting occurrence was observed with *M. euphorbiae*, between the dry and rainy seasons (Table 1.0).

Table 1.0: Raw data on overall mean insect abundance in the dry and rainy seasons of 2024.

Insect pest species	Seasons	
	Dry season	Rainy season
<i>E. fabae</i> (Leafhopper)	35.8%	33.6%
<i>M. euphorbiae</i> (Aphid)	31.4%	17.2%
<i>B. tabaci</i> (Whitefly)	23.7%	18.9%

Mean insect pest abundance according to seasons and years revealed significantly (P<0.05) higher insect pests recorded in the dry season (Table 2.0). Revealing that more number of insects were recorded in the periods of dry season (27.18 ±2.53), significantly higher (p<0.05), that of the rainy season abundance (21.13±2.14). In contrasts insect abundance in the dry (20.27±2.06) and rainy (19.17±1.76) season did not significantly differ (P<0.05) indicating similar abundance in both the two different seasons (Table 2.0).

Table 2.0: Abundance of insect pest species on tomato as affected by seasons in 2024.

Season	Mean abundance in 2017 ± S.E	Mean abundance in 2018 ± S.E
Rainy season	21.13±2.14b	19.17±1.76 a
Dry season	27.18±2.53a	20.27±2.06a

Note: Means with similar letter(s) within column are not significantly different using LSD = Least Significant Difference at p=0.05 level of Probability.

Results in Table 3.0 below shows individual insect pest abundance obtained during the dry and rainy seasons of 2024 had revealed different outcomes. There was a significant differences (p<0.05) in the number of individuals obtained between species in dry and rainy season in both years. Leaf hopper *E. fabae* was significantly the highest in abundance in both dry (48.93%) and rainy (38.33%) rainy seasons. The abundance of Aphid *M. euphorbiae* was the second highest in the dry (37.35%) and rainy (25.57)

seasons on tomato. With Whitefly *B. tabaci* during the dry (21.33%) and rainy (23.23%) seasons recorded as the third most abundant insect pest on tomato in the study area during the study. (Table 3.0).

Table 1.0: Abundance of insect pest species on tomato in the rainy season of 2024

Insect species	Dry season	Rainy season
<i>E. fabae</i>	48.93±3.23 ^a	38.33±2.55 ^a
<i>M. euphorbiae</i>	37.35±2.65 ^b	25.57±1.33 ^b
<i>B. tabaci</i>	21.33±2.15 ^c	23.23±1.33 ^b

Note: Means with similar letter within same column are not significantly different using LSD = Least Significant Difference at p=0.05 level of Probability.

DISCUSSION

The effects of climatic factors; temperature, relative humidity on the abundance of the three major insect pests of tomato monitored in the study area favoured higher abundance of these small body-size insect namely; Leafhopper (*E. fabae*), Aphid (*M. euphorbiae*) and Whitefly (*B. tabaci*) by influencing, dictating and determining their physical and physiological activities of the insect larvae and adults, insect movements, phenology and period of development and ability to endure severe weather factors that determining insect population with rainfall been very suppressive to thee smaller sized insects as strongly supported by the findings of Sanjeeb *et al.* (2019). Higher abundance of insect pests on tomato obtained in this study temperatures may likely be attributed to the higher temperatures because temperature and body weight of an insect are the most prominent determinants of metabolism, development, reproduction, population growth and species diversity, as reported by Wade (2020), temperature and the relative humidity had positive significant effect on the abundance of *B. tabaci* on tomato. This study is further supported by the findings of Khan *et al.* (2019), who stated that abiotic factors such as average temperature and average relative humidity had a strong positive and linear relationship with the abundance of *B. tabaci* on tomato.

Weather factors like temperature and relative humidity, mainly encourage insect population growth or lead to reduction in population, during the warm and dry weather where these insect activities increased significantly as observed in this study. Similarly, the outcome of this study shows that temperature and relative humidity favoured the highest insect pest abundance during the dry season. Abiotic factors regulate insect population which are responsible for many physiological and enzymatic activities in insect bodies (Khan and Hossain, 2019). Temperature was found to be the major climatic factor playing the role of determining insect abundance, with relative humidity having direct and indirect impact on insect growth, development, survival, behaviour, reproduction and population ecology of insects as key players in insect abundance (Zeshwan *et al.*, 2015). In a related study, temperature was reported to be the dynamic driving power behind insect development, growth and behavior and this is because insects are poikilothermic (“cold-blooded”); meaning they are not capable of regulating their outside body temperature and internal temperatures varying with the ambient environmental temperature (Sanjeeb *et al.*, 2019). This study revealed dry season as the most conducive period for small bodied insect due to high fecundity, facilitating growth, development leading to the highest abundance synergized by the complete absence of rainfall that significantly reduces insect pest abundance.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation has indicated variable abundance of the three different insect pests monitored and recorded on tomato plants in the field that were identified and studied during both dry and rainy seasons of 2024 in the study location. The major insect pests of tomato monitored in the study field were; Potato Leafhopper (*Empoasca fabae*), Tomato Aphid (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*) and Silverleaf Whitefly (*B. tabaci*). These insect pests were found to attack tomato plant in the study field having different abundance on tomato plants in both the dry and rainy seasons.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Timing of Leafhopper, Aphid and Whitefly control strategies should be performed before it reaches its peak population build-up specifically before the end of the rainy season periods and towards the beginning of the dry seasons as this will substantially assist in bringing down the population of *B. tabaci* to the lowest level in the study location.

Tomato insects especially Leafhopper, Aphid and Whitefly control strategies should be initiated in the study site as it recorded the highest abundance as the pest can be a source of concerns in tomato production in the study site.

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